

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

(To be filled in and uploaded as deliverable in the Portal Grant Management System, at the due date foreseen in the system (and regularly updated).)

⚠ The template is recommended but not mandatory. If you do not use it, please make however sure that you comply with the research data management requirements under Article 17 of the Grant Agreement.)

PROJECT	
Project number:	101105296
Project acronym:	OH-GENDER
Project name:	Investigation into reasons for drinking among adolescents and young adults: a gender perspective.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN	
Date:	12/02/2024
Version:	DMP version 1

1. Data Summary

OH-GENDER will work with:

- a set of data based on another set of data (literature review to develop the assessment instrument)
- collected data sets (collection of personal data and generated research data)
- Generated project data (distinct information stored in a different data set).

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

Yes, a systematic review will be carried out to obtain a quality theoretical basis for the development of the instrument, foreseen in the project. This work will be according to Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) and will be sent to a high-impact journal.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

- Re-use of literature-based research data collected from peer-reviewed scientific publications; the formats are ris, PDFs, XML, HTML, graphic and images.
- Collection of personal data: sociodemographic characteristics, consumption patterns; the format will be PDF, graphic, images, database codebook of variables and variable values codebook in csv, and README.txt.
- Research data generated: assessment variables using measuring instruments (reasons that lead to alcohol consumption, impulsivity, personality); the format will be PDF, graphic, images, database codebook of variables and variable values codebook in csv, and README.txt.
- Project data generated: reports with dissemination and project results intended for the scientific, professional community, and citizens; the format will be PDF, graphic, images.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- Re-use of literature-based research data collected from scientific publications:

The purpose of reusing this data is to generate a robust theoretical basis for the development of the

evaluation instrument that will be developed to answer objectives, 1 "To develop a new instrument (Gender Gap in Alcohol Consumption Questionnaire- GGAC-Q)" e 2 "To evaluate the psychometric properties of GGAC-Q", of OH-GENDER.

- Collection of personal data: sociodemographic characteristics, consumption pattern:

The objective of collecting participants' personal data is to characterize the sample studied, enabling extrapolation and comparison of data with other populations. Includes the 3rd objective of the project "To determine the relationships between alcohol consumption and different variables"

- Research data generated: assessment variables using measuring instruments (reasons that lead to alcohol consumption, impulsivity, personality):

These data will be essential to obtain sufficient information to correlate variables and identify determinants of alcohol consumption. Through these variables, it will be possible to propose a model using mediating and moderating variables of alcohol consumption from a gender perspective. Making it possible to completely achieve the 3rd objective of the project.

- Project data generated: reports with dissemination and project results intended for the scientific, professional community and citizens:

These data are primarily purpose the dissemination and exploitation of the activities and results OH-GENDER project. The reports are intended to sensitize the population to participate in the study through dissemination materials. The presentation of the results seeks to raise awareness with a focus on understanding how alcohol consumption; show the reality of alcohol consumption in participating populations, and present possibilities for prevention actions. Furthermore, the objective is to make knowledge accessible to the scientific and professional communities and citizens.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The project is expected to achieve a total data size of up to 1 GB.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

- Re-use of literature-based research data: The data come from electronic scientific databases (PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus and Dialnet electronic databases). For the purposes of enabling open science, a registration in the International Prospective Registry of Systematic Reviews: Prospero. Data collection was carried out by the two researchers involved in OH-GENDER and a collaborating researcher. This work was crucial for building a solid theoretical basis for later developing the assessment instrument "(Gender Gap in Alcohol Consumption Questionnaire--GGAC-Q)" proposed in the project.

- Collection of Personal Data and Research data generated:

The research data will be generated from measurement instruments applied to adolescents from secondary schools in the city of Valencia and young students from the University of Valencia. The presentation of the questionnaires will be carried out by the project researcher, however, data collection will take place in an online format. This data will be fundamental for validating the assessment instrument and making it possible to propose an innovative model based on the determinants of alcohol consumption from a gender perspective. Furthermore, with this data, it will also be possible to examine the relationships between alcohol consumption and different moderating and mediating variables (such as gender roles, age, attachment, self-esteem, impulsivity, expectations, and consumption pattern).

- Project data generated:

The project data generated are those collected at project events, such as visits to schools and universities and workshops. The data collected will only be that which is extremely relevant and

necessary for contact and dissemination of the project if authorized in advance. They will also be useful for understanding the characterization and scope of the project results.

We will use the LimeSurvey program (WP2-OH-GENDER) where data will be automatically recorded, stored and managed later. All processes will be online and anonymous. European data protection rules (Regulation EU2016/679) will be followed and all participants must accept informed consent before starting to answer the questionnaires.

A data dictionary will be previously created to identify and describe each variable, as well as a description of the entire statistical analysis process.

Soon after collection, the data will be processed (verified and categorized) and sent to the IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 23.0 and MPlus software data analysis program.

Furthermore, the data will be made available on the Roderic UV and Zotero UE platforms so that the principle of open science is covered.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Data from the OH-GENDER are valuable for other researchers to understand aspects related to alcohol consumption and gender gap, and can complement existing qualitative research and thus offer the possibility of comparison between groups of people and populations in new studies. Throughout the project, we will seek the good practice of open science so that any professional or researcher who is interested in replicating the research can reproduce it. Citizens can also benefit from these data, both teenagers, schools, health and education professionals, and parents, as they will secondarily be able to have an overview of the current situation of alcohol consumption in this population and how boys and girls are thinking about it. Furthermore, these data could support governments, managers, and health professionals in general in developing specific prevention programs for adolescent boys and girls, as well as better-targeted action plans.

2. FAIR data

1.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

OH-GENDER intends to publish its database in two open-access repositories, ZENODO (<https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>) and RODERIC (<https://roderic.uv.es/home>). The metadata of these platforms uses a Digital Object Identifier. These platforms use rich metadata that are: Author, title, publication date, Unique identifier (DOI, Handle), License (CC- by) so that it can be reused, File format (CSV, txt, SAV, etc.), Description of the data set, Keywords, Description of the variables that compose them, finance information. The syntaxes of the study will be created following disciplinary standards, and will also be available in open-access repositories. This action will optimize the possibility of discovery and then potential reuse. The metadata will be offered so that it can be harvested and indexed. Furthermore, the project's results will be presented in open-access publications and identified by a DOI, and whenever permitted, researchers will also make them available on their social networks.

1.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

While choosing repositories, we considered adhering to FAIR data principles. The selected repositories were developed to facilitate the discovery, access, reuse, and interoperability of datasets. They allow the deposit of

different types of publications, such as scientific articles and data dissemination materials, as well as datasets. Additionally, you can link these items through persistent identifiers and data citations, and add alternative persistent identifier information and links to related persistent identifiers. They have DOIs for all uploads and deposited records.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Will all data of the OH-GENDER will be made openly available. The only embargo, if it occurs, will be due to the need of the journal (editor). No sensitive data will be collected, data will be collected anonymously and online. If any new situation is identified, it will be informed when updating this plan.

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

OH_GENDER will make metadata and repositories licensed under a CC by public domain dedication openly available. Metadata will contain information to allow user access, such as data, title/volume/edition/pages/acronym/dates/keyword.

The chosen repositories keep the data open permanently.

OH-GENDER will not include a reference to the software because it is not necessary as FAIR principles will be used.

1.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data

interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

For interoperability the OH_GENDER will use a methodology accessible, shared, and of the standardised languages. In addition, to show knowledge will use formal and broadly language. This will make it possible to exchange, interpret, and share the data. All data will be presented in English, the most universal language. However, considering the projection of use in different scenarios, the language will be adapted according to the profile of the target population.

Furthermore, when necessary, shown in two languages: English, and Spanish, which is the language in which the study will be applied. This makes the data fully accessible, in this case, for example, reports for schools, families, and teenagers. Additionally, the researchers involved in the project took a training course provided by the University of Valencia to become skilled in writing accessible documents.

A controlled data vocabulary will be used to describe the datasets, this will be documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers. This documentation will be made available in online format in the repositories and will therefore be easily findable and accessible by anyone using the dataset. In addition, whenever possible, records will be made and protocol will be published for the work carried out, always in an open, free, and universal manner.

The ZENODO and RODERIC platforms, choosing for OH_GENDER, follow interoperability best practices based on FAIR principles.

OH-GENDER does not forecast the use of unusual ontologies or vocabularies, however, if this occurs, mappings will be provided and published openly to allow their reuse, refinement, or extension.

Qualified references will be made available, always fully explaining their intention. OH-GENDER will create as many links as possible between data resources to enrich contextual knowledge about the data and create a good data model.

Scientific links between datasets will be described and cited including their unique and persistent global identifiers.

1.4. Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

Validation of data analysis will be provided with readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data dictionary, data cleaning, analyses description, variable definitions, and units of measurement, to facilitate data reuse as much as possible.

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

The OH-GENDER data will be freely available in the public domain on ZENODO and RODERIC to enable the widest possible reuse. It will be licensed under standard reuse licences as mandated by the Grant Agreement (CC BY).

The data will be published in peer-reviewed open-access journals, and after publication will be deposited in the repositories. The data produced in the project will be anonymized to ensure data security and ethical compliance and will be usable by third parties. The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using appropriate standards according to FAIR principles.

2. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

The OH-GENDER predicts, in addition to publications in open peer-reviewed journals, publication in journals aimed at professionals and also open access. This will make it possible to have an impact beyond the scientific community. In addition, we also provide informative reports for participating school centers, students, teachers, and parents. All of these publications will follow FAIR principles. The results will be managed considering ethical standards, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 relating to the protection of individuals about the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data (GDPR),

Organic Law 3/2018, of December 5, on the Protection of Personal Data and guarantee of digital rights, and Guide to good practices in the field of Transparency and Data Protection. Edited by CRUE. Furthermore, the anonymization process will always be carried out. The results will be shared online and also through the Zenodo and Roderic repositories to enable their re-use.

3. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

The data repository used by OH-GENDER offers free-of-charge, and open storage for research data. The preservation policies of the platforms that will be used by OH-GENDER inform that they provide permanent access to deposited documents, so that records are not deleted, except for some exceptions (They are not relevant to the nature of the platform; They support a format whose archive or display is absolutely unsatisfactory in platform; They contain a virus or have any other technical problem. Infringing copyright; They are plagiarism of other authors' works, and Duplicate jobs.) Scientific papers that are open-access and present the project's research findings will be funded from the project's available budget. The team members responsible for OH-GENDER data management are the two researchers involved in the project.

4. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

To ensure data security, data recovery, storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data OH-GENDER will use

programa LimeSurvey. This program is an open-source online survey application that allows users to create, customize, and distribute surveys for various purposes. It offers a wide range of features and functionalities to help users collect and analyze data effectively. The University of Valencia has a licence for use since this program implements various measures to protect user data. They regularly update their software to address any security vulnerabilities and provide options for encryption and secure data transmission. The data will be

safely stored in trusted repositories, ZENODO and RODERIC for long term preservation and curation. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) will always be followed.

5. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

There are no any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? In case they are identified, they will be described in the updated plan. The informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be included in questionnaires when pertinent.

6. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

The OH-GENDER project will not use other procedures.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	CHANGE
1.0	21.06.24	Initial version

Date & Signature of fellow

Date & Signature of supervisor